

Pyrazolo-Thiazoles

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Some Pyrazolo(3,4-d)-thiazoles have been synthesised by the condensation of phenyl thioureas with 4-bromo-1,3 diphenyl pyrazolone-5. However, in each case, two products have been isolated. Both the products have been assigned proper structure on the basis of I.R. Spectra and analytical results. One of the two products has also been synthesised by an unambiguous route.

ALTHOUGH a good deal of work has been carried out towards the synthesis of pyrazolo(4,3-d)-thiazoles¹⁻⁴, the work on isomeric pyrazolo(3,4-d)-thiazoles has attracted little attention. The only reference that seems to be available towards the synthesis of pyrazolo(3,4-d)-thiazoles is by Moskalenko *et al.*⁵

simple method involving the condensation of phenyl thioureas (III) with 4-bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 (II), the latter in turn was obtained by the bromination of 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5(I).

The first step would be the formation of the thiourea derivative IV which could cyclise in two ways to give rise to either V or VI. Actually, condensation gave rise to two products i.e., when the condensation is carried out in ethanol, one of the two products separates out. It has a higher melting point. It gradually dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution and gets reprecipitated upon acidification with acetic acid. It shows an I.R. absorption band at 1665-1645 cm⁻¹ characteristic of thiazolone ring. Thus, the product has been assigned the structure VII which is presumably formed by the hydrolysis of the intermediate imine VI.

The filtrate upon concentration gives rise to another product which does not dissolve in sodium hydroxide. It does not show any I.R. absorption band in 1665-1640 cm⁻¹ region. It has been assigned the structure V which is supported on the basis of analytical results and I.R. absorption band for N-H at 3450-3420 cm⁻¹.

The structure V has been confirmed by preparing one of the compounds by an unambiguous route involving the condensation of IX and X; IX in turn was obtained by treatment of II with potassium

Keeping in view the chemotherapeutic importance of this system, some new pyrazolo(3,4-d)-thiazoles have been synthesised, in the present case, by a very

sulphocyanide and passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through cold ethereal solution of the resultant product VIII.

The identity of the products V formed by different routes was confirmed by their m.p., m.m.p. and superimposable I.R. spectra.

In fact, solubility of the first product in sodium hydroxide suggests the possibility of having structure XI or XII also.

FIG. 3

But it is a common observation⁶ that systems like $\begin{matrix} S \\ || \\ RNH-C- \end{matrix}$ react with halo compounds at SH but with enolic OH, it is the NH which is involved. Moreover, I.R. spectrum does not show any absorption band at 2550–2600 cm^{-1} characteristic of SH which rules out the possibility of XI and XII.

Experimental

4-Bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5(II): A solution of bromine (4 ml) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was

added little by little to a solution of 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5⁷ (20 g.) in 200 ml of the same solvent at 10°–12°. The contents were kept at room temperature overnight. After diluting it with water (100 ml) and cooling in ice bath, the product was filtered under suction and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 110°, yield being 19.2 g. (Found: N, 8.98; $C_{15}H_{11}BrN_2O$ requires N, 8.88%).

Condensation of phenyl thiourea with 4-bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 i.e., isolation of 1,3,6-triphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazolone-5(VII) and 5-anilino 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazole (V): A solution of phenyl thiourea (0.4 g) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with a solution of 4-bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 (0.83 g) in 30 ml of the same solvent. Immediately the colour changed from green to red. The contents were refluxed for 5 hrs. After cooling, the product was filtered under suction and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 330°. It is soluble in sodium hydroxide and has been assigned the structure VII.

Alcohol was distilled off from the mother liquor and the residue was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 145°. This product is insoluble in sodium hydroxide and has been assigned the structure V.

Other phenyl substituted thioureas have also been condensed with 4-bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 under identical conditions.

The data regarding both series of pyrazolo-thiazoles is tabulated in Table 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1—1,3-DIPHENYL 6-ARYL PYRAZOLO (3,4-D)THIAZOLONE-5 (VII)

Sl.No.	Thiourea used	Ar	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
						Found %	Reqd.%
1.	Phenyl thiourea	C_6H_5	20	330	$C_{22}H_{15}N_3OS$	N, 11.32	11.38
2.	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	28	324	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3OS$	N, 11.46	10.97
3.	<i>m</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>m</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	17	330	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3OS$	N, 10.72	10.97
4.	<i>o</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>o</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	23	325	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3OS$	N, 11.01	10.97
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $CH_3O-C_6H_4$	31	312	$C_{23}H_{17}N_3O_2S$	N, 10.41	10.53
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $C_2H_5O-C_6H_4$	29	306	$C_{24}H_{19}N_3O_2S$	C, 69.49 H, 4.42 N, 10.31	69.73 4.60 10.17

All these compounds have been crystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE 2—5-AMINO 1,3-DIPHENYL PYRAZOLO (3,4-D) THIAZOLE (V)

Sl.No.	Thiourea used	Ar	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
						Found%	Reqd.%
1.	Phenyl thiourea	C_6H_5	32	145	$C_{22}H_{16}N_4S$	N, 15.01	15.22
2.	<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	35	130	$C_{23}H_{18}N_4S$	C, 71.93 H, 4.99 N, 14.23	72.25 4.71 14.66
3.	<i>m</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>m</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	22	95	$C_{23}H_{18}N_4S$	N, 14.28	14.66
4.	<i>o</i> -Methyl phenyl thiourea	<i>o</i> - $CH_3-C_6H_4$	30	147	$C_{23}H_{18}N_4S$	N, 14.40	14.66
5.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $CH_3O-C_6H_4$	39	121	$C_{23}H_{18}N_4OS$	N, 14.29	14.07
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy phenyl thiourea	<i>p</i> - $C_2H_5O-C_6H_4$	34	100	$C_{24}H_{20}N_4OS$	N, 13.37	13.69

All these compounds have been crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ethyl acetate.

4-Thiocyano 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 (VIII): A solution of potassium sulphocyanide (1.06 g) in water (2 ml) was added to a solution of 4-bromo 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 (3.15 g) in ethanol (30 ml) at 40°. After shaking it thoroughly, the contents were kept at room temperature overnight. The product was filtered under suction and crystallised from dilute ethanol m.p. 144°, yield 2.05 g. (Found : N, 14.01; C₁₆H₁₁N₃OS requires N, 14.33%).

5-Chloro 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazole (IX): A cold suspension of 4-thiocyano 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolone-5 (2 g) in dry ether (50 ml) was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. After keeping it at room temperature overnight, the ether was evaporated off and the residue was basified with sodium carbonate solution. It was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 130°, yield 1.60 g. (Found : N, 13.61; C₁₆H₁₀ClN₃S requires N, 13.48%).

Condensation of 5-chloro 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazole with o-toluidine i.e., isolation of 5 (o-toluidino)-1,3-diphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazole (V): A mixture of 5-chloro 1,3-diphenyl pyrazolo (3,4-d)-thiazole (1.50 g), o-toluidine (0.51 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was heated on an oil bath at 130° for 3 hrs. After cooling the product was neutralised with sodium carbonate solution and

collected under suction. It was washed with water and crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 140°, yield 0.74 g. It was found to be identical with the sodium hydroxide insoluble product obtained in experiment 2 by its m.m.p. and superimposable I.R. spectrum.

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